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Scaling-up Of A Highly Modular Rotating Packed Bed Plant With An Efficient Solvent For Capture Cost Reduction: An Overview of the HiRECORD Project

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Abstract

Rotating Packed Beds (RPBs) are emerging as a promising alternative for CO₂ capture, due to the intense centrifugal force that is generated as they spin, which significantly enhances the mass transfer and greatly facilitates CO₂ absorption. RPBs are expected to enable over 10-15 times lower volume compared to conventional packed beds of the same capture efficiency, allowing a reduction in capture costs. To date very few 1.0 tCO₂/d demonstrations of RPB units and plants have been reported. Project HiRECORD is developing a 10.0 t CO₂/d capture pilot plant that is based on advanced RPB technologies for absorption and desorption. This will be demonstrated in three industrial sites that emit flue gases of different specifications. This work highlights the features of the pilot plant and of the industrial sites. It also provides an overview of various complementary research activities pertaining to solvent testing, development of thermodynamic and process models and sustainability assessment.

Keywords: CO₂ capture, Rotating Packed Bed, Demonstration

The European Commission has committed to a climate neutral economy with net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050¹. Carbon capture systems are expected to play a significant role to this end, but the wide industrial deployment of such plants remains

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elusive². Compared to other capture technologies, solvent-based CO₂ capture exhibits sufficient maturity for short-term deployment². Despite the progress made in the past, significant reductions are still necessary in both capital and operational capture costs to enable wide proliferation of capture plants in industry³. Such requirements are largely associated with the predominant use of packed-bed (PB) columns in existing demonstration plants, which incur significant capital costs and use of resources due to their large size (height and volume).

Rotating Packed Beds (RPBs) are emerging as a promising alternative for CO₂ capture⁴, due to the intense centrifugal field that is generated as they spin, which significantly enhances the mass transfer and greatly facilitates CO₂ absorption⁴. As a result, RPBs are expected to enable over 10-15 times lower volume compared to PBs of same capture efficiency, with significant benefits on capital costs as well as consumption of resources. Despite their advantages, RPB absorbers and desorbers have mostly been investigated separately and in lab-scale units⁵, whereas very few 1.0 tCO₂/d demonstrations of RPB units and plants have been reported previously with the participation of some of the co-authors^{6,7}.

The current work aims to highlight the current progress of the EU- and UK-funded HiRECORD project that will demonstrate a 10t/d CO₂ capture plant that uses RPBs for absorption and desorption and operates with the commercial APBS-CDRMax[®] solvent. The plant has unique design features, such as the dual absorber and the advanced RPB desorber with integrated stripper and reboiler (RPB-ISR) (Figure 1a). The dual absorber enables interstage cooling which is known to improve CO₂ capture efficiency, to reduce regeneration energy requirements and to help lower solvent degradation and emissions from the absorber. The basic idea of the RPB-ISR is to directly heat the walls of the solvent regenerator (stripper) so that the energy required for heating the solvent and removing CO₂ is supplied directly rather than indirectly via a separate reboiler. One advantage of this layout is that the temperature difference between the solvent and the steam used to heat it can be lower because there is no requirement to generate vapour at pressure. Furthermore, there are no heat losses from the walls of the column as there would be if they were separate units. Both of these factors act to reduce the energy consumption compared to an RPB desorber with an external reboiler. Another significant feature is the modular skid design, which allows for significant space reduction. The plant will be delivered to the demo sites in the form of easy to assemble skids based on standard ISO frames. A 3D drawing of the plant skid is shown in Figure 1b.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: a) 1 t/d RPB-ISR, b) 3D overview of pilot plant skid

The plant will be demonstrated on the premises of three industrial users that have different flue gas specifications and challenging operating requirements. The first demonstration will be performed in a quicklime production plant, at the CaO Hellas site (Greece). The production is performed through combustion of the raw material with fuel and air in a double vertical chamber, where the hot air produced during combustion in the first chamber is used to preheat the second chamber before combustion begins. This periodicity in operation means that the flow of CO₂ (concentration 12-15 vol. %) into the capture plant is not continuous, but essentially the plant would need to operate in a semi-batch mode. The flue gases may also contain solids and other contaminants that may challenge the capture plant's operation if even traces elude the pre-separation systems. The second demonstration will be performed in a natural gas combined cycle power plant, in the Elpedison site (Greece), which has very dilute flue gases with CO₂ concentration around 4 vol. %. Periodical operation is the norm for the power plant, as it offers back-up power to the grid and enters operation whenever it is requested by the national grid authority. The final demonstration will be performed in a refinery setting, through flue gases that are generated by an industrial boiler. The design of the skid and the operation regime developed will need to address all the above challenges. At the same time, the design would need to be performed in order to meet several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) pertaining to capture rate of 90% and 95%, reboiler duty close to 2.1 GJ/tCO₂ and considerably lower corrosion than 30 wt.% MEA solvent, among others. Preliminary data show that the RPB-ISR may enable 15% lower reboiler

duty compared to a conventional reboiler. The APBS-CDRMax[®] solvent is also showing in current work considerably lower corrosion rates in SS 316 L compared to MEA, in the presence of CO₂, sulfur and nitric oxides at high concentrations, in lab experiments designed to mimic the acid gas species typically found in industrial flue gases.

The project also has an intense program where significant developments are in progress around models needed to capture the complex thermodynamic interactions of real flue gases with amine solvents and also in process models for RPB plants. A thermodynamic model is developed based on the group contribution SAFT- γ Mie equation of state⁸ that accounts for the first time for the interactions of CO₂ and amines with nitric and sulfur oxides. This model uses the predictive power of the group contribution equation of state^{9,10} to derive model parameters based on a small amount of phase equilibria data. Steady-state and dynamic RPB models are also developed that exhibit good fit to experimental data, providing a venue for simulation of such capture processes under realistic operating specifications. Such models are also being employed for sustainability studies, while the electrification of the capture plant is also being explored through the use of heat pumps to perform internal heat recovery and further reduce the parasitic resources consumption.

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